

Hidden Dangers of Tap Water

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Abstract:- Drinking water quality is one of the major factors affecting human health. However, drinking water quality is undesirable in many countries, especially in developing countries, and poor drinking water quality causes many water-borne diseases. This special issue on exposure and health provides a better understanding of the impact of drinking water quality on public health and the ability to take appropriate steps to improve drinking water quality in many countries. This editorial introduction reviews some of the latest research on drinking water quality and public health, briefly summarizes the gist of each article in this issue, and then further scientifically on drinking water quality and public health.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is no secret that drinking water is important to your health. After all, water accounts for about two thirds of the total human body weight. It is used to control metabolism, aid digestion, repair damaged tissue and more. But if you are currently drinking tap water in your home, you may want to reconsider your H₂O source. The tap water in the United States should be safe to use, but the fact is that American tap water is full of pollutants including sewage, lead, pesticides, and other potentially harmful substances. To raise awareness of the problem. The drinking water contaminants that can have chronic effects include chemicals (such as disinfection byproducts, solvents and pesticides), radionuclides (such as radium), and minerals (such as arsenic). Examples of these chronic effects include cancer, liver or kidney problems, or reproductive difficulties.

II. IS THE SOURCE CURRENT?

New Study Reveals Cancer-Causing Compounds in Tap Water According to a new study by the Environmental Working Group (EWG), tap water often contains one or more cancer-causing compounds. In the study, researchers tested tap water samples from more than 48,000 water systems in the United States. After analyzing the samples, they found 22 cancer-causing compounds. The EWG estimates that up to 4 out of 10,000 Americans will get cancer from drinking contaminated tap water. Although these findings are relevant, it is even more relevant that many of these cancer-stricken samples still meet legal standards.

III. WHO WAS THE ARTICLE WRITTEN FOR?

An article is a piece of text written for a wide audience. The main purpose of writing a story is to be published in newspapers or magazines or journals to make a difference in the world. My article is written for the scientist to help them find a solution for replacing tap water.

IV. SOLUTION FOR REPLACING TAP WATER

A. What About Bottled Water?

Many people think that bottled water is safe to drink than tap water. When processed and packaged by a well-known beverage company, common sense may lead you to believe that it contains no carcinogen and other contaminants. Unfortunately, however, this is not the case. Bottled water usually contains nothing but tap water. Beverage companies simply fill bottles with tap water, after which they distribute them and sell them as bottles.

Of course, bottled water is also less harmful. Statistics show that an estimated 38 million water bottles, most of which are made of plastic, end up in the garbage dump every year. It has become so big that many cities are now taking steps to restrict or restrict the use of once-used plastic water bottles.

B. Drink Filtered Tap Water

Instead of drinking bottled water, consider drinking filtered tap water. There are several different types of water filtration systems, some of which include activated carbon, ultraviolet (UV), infrared (IR) and reversible osmosis. Regardless, they are all designed to clean tap water by removing harmful chemicals and compounds. By investing in a water filtration system, you can enjoy clean and fresh tap water without fear of injecting harmful chemicals or compounds unintentionally.

C. Opinion on Hidden Dangers of Tap Water

Evidence suggests that fluoride from our tap water is directly linked to osteosarcoma (bone cancer), low IQ in children, high fertility rate, premature birth, high percentages of low birth weight, Arthritis, Heart Disease, Fractured Arthritis, helps to grow. of plants, increases the risk of fractures, suppresses thyroid gland and lowers your immune system to fight germs.

D. Can you get cancer from tap water?

Most tap water meets the legal standards set by the federal government, but EWG researchers have found that the contaminants present in tap water pose a measurable risk of cancer. EPA plans to regulate carcinogenic chemicals in drinking water in the United States. In a previous study conducted by the EWG, a cumulative analysis of pollutants in tap water in California put a risk of 15,000 cancers. It became clear that it would increase.

Experts say the risks of these carcinogens have been debated for decades. They point out that the standards for municipal water systems, which are nationally regulated by the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), are complex and require a balance between cost and safety.

E. Is Clean water is complicated?

In recent years, several crises have revealed the complexity and failure of managing public water systems, from the various water sources used by the community to the pipes that carry water to the home. The EPA regulates public drinking water under the Safe Drinking Water Act of 1974. The EPA requires that pollutant standards be established through national primary drinking water regulations, thereby minimizing exposure to pollutants.

V. CURRENT DATA OF PEOPLE USING TAP WATER

Community Water Services (Cws) Are Community Water Services That Provide Water To The Same People All Year Round. In The 2019 Financial Year (Fy), Over 310 Million Americans (U.S. Epa, 2020a) —About 94 Percent Of U.S. Population (U.S. Census Bureau, 2019) —Find At Least Cws Drinking Water. This Index Identifies The Percentage Of Americans Who Are Affiliated. Cws When It Says No Violation Of Epa Health-Based Standards For Pollution Of More Than 90 (U.S. Epa, 2020a).

In the national census conducted by CWS nationally, the percentage provided to systems that have not been reported for annual health-based violations increased from 79 percent in 1993 to 92 percent in FY 2019 (Exhibit 1). Regulations for drinking water have changed in recent years. This indicator is based on reported violations of applicable standards in any year.

VI. CONCLUSION

As the industry continues to evolve, more and more chemicals that have never been considered contaminated will be released into the environment such as poly-cyclic aromatics hydrocarbons, pharmaceuticals and cosmetics. Some of these chemicals can be harmful to humans and / or the environment. Therefore, emerging pollutants that are highly different from toxins, behaviours and remedial measures should be carefully considered in terms of their impact on human health and the mechanisms / exposure mechanisms of threat to public health. Many research projects should be funded by organizations and agencies and close

cooperation between scientists, governments and the general public should be particularly encouraged.

REFERENCES

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